

Title : Effect of iron deficiency anaemia on glycated haemoglobin in the Indian population: A systematic review

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Abstract:

Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) is considered the gold standard to measure long term glycaemic status over three months, Iron deficiency anaemia can affect glycated haemoglobin levels independently of glycaemic status which complicates diagnosis of diabetes mellitus. The primary objective of this systematic review is to determine the association of iron deficiency anaemia with HbA1c levels in Indian population. A comprehensive search was conducted on databases such as PubMed, Cochrane, Embase, Google scholar using keywords related to iron deficiency anaemia, HbA1c, and India. Studies meeting inclusion criteria were screened and referenced using the Zotero software. Risk of bias was assessed using the ROBINS E for experimental studies and ROBINS I for interventional studies, by at least two people with a process to resolve differences. The review was registered with PROSPERO with registration number CRD420251159232. A total of 16 cross-sectional and case control studies were included in the paper. . The majority of the interventional studies showed a low risk of bias but experimental studies assessed by showed a very high risk of bias. Quantitative analysis of studies yielded a pooled effect size of 0.76 across studies (95% CI), indicating IDA increases HbA1c levels in Indian population. This systematic review emphasized the importance of screening for iron deficiency anaemia prior to the evaluation of diabetes mellitus via HbA1c. By gathering information exclusively from Indian studies, it aimed to provide insights that are beneficial for clinical practice and public health in India. Future research should focus on comprehensive, multicentric, and methodologically sound studies that can corroborate these findings globally and reduce the risk of false positive /false negatives in screening for diabetes mellitus via HbA1c.

Keywords

Iron deficiency anaemia; Haemoglobin A1c; Glycated hemoglobin; Glycation End Products;
Diabetic; Nondiabetics

Introduction

1.1 Background and rationale :

Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) is the gold standard for monitoring long-term glycaemic control . It measures serum glucose levels over the previous three months.[1,2] . In diabetes mellitus (DM), there is an increase in blood glucose (hyperglycaemia). This causes more glucose to bind to haemoglobin. Therefore, elevated HbA1c levels (>6.5%) are associated with greater risk of developing complications of diabetes mellitus.[3]

Iron deficiency anaemia (IDA)is one of the most common forms of anaemia worldwide[3,4]. In addition to the WHO criteria, a low serum ferritin(<9 ng/mL for females; <15 ng/mL for males) in the Indian population is essential for its diagnosis.[5] According to Sharma et al, its global prevalence has been estimated to be 250 per 1000 live births [6] .It is characterized by reduced iron stores and haemoglobin levels. A narrative review by Natekar et al in 2022, stated that lack of iron rich foods in diet was the leading cause of IDA in developing nations.[7] Increased blood loss during menstruation is also a major cause of IDA in women in the reproductive age group. The pathogenesis of IDA is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Pathogenesis of iron deficiency anaemia

1.2 Need for the study: dual burden of IDA and HbA1c in India

India, presents a unique epidemiological profile. The region reports a high prevalence of diabetes (10–30% in urban areas)[8] alongside widespread iron deficiency anaemia (affecting up to 50% of women and children in certain communities). The potential for IDA to skew HbA1c measurements could lead to misdiagnosis or mismanagement of diabetes, underscoring the need to investigate this relationship in the Indian population.

1.3 Objectives of the Systematic Review

This systematic review aimed to comprehensively evaluate the impact of iron deficiency anaemia on glycated haemoglobin levels in the South Indian population.

The specific objectives are outlined below

Primary objective

The primary objective of this systematic review was to determine the impact of iron deficiency anaemia on HbA1c levels in Indian population.

Secondary objectives

- To analyse variations in the IDA-HbA1c relationship across subgroups, such as age, gender, and diabetic versus non-diabetic populations.
- To investigate the mechanisms by which IDA may affect HbA1c measurements, including alterations in red blood cell lifespan and glycation processes.
- To identify limitations in current research studies and provide evidence-based insights to improve diagnostic accuracy and inform targeted interventions for managing IDA and diabetes in the Indian population.

1.4 Materials and methods

- **Eligibility criteria:**

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were identified based on a modified version of the PICO framework (**Population, Intervention, Control and Outcome**) to ensure a systematic and focussed approach to study selection.

Inclusion criteria

- Studies involving human participants diagnosed with Iron deficiency anaemia of any age and gender according to the WHO guidelines. (Hb < 12g/dL in females and < 13 g/dL in adult males) and low serum ferritin (<9 ng/mL for females; <15 ng/mL for males) in the Indian population. [5]
- Studies using cutoff value of HbA1c(>6.5%) to diagnose diabetes as per American Diabetes Association (ADA criteria)[9]

Intervention(I)/ Exposure (E):

- Presence of IDA as the exposure/condition under study
- Presence of HbA1c as the primary investigation to assess blood glucose levels.

Comparison(C):

Case control studies

- **Selection of cases** : Individuals diagnosed with IDA as per the WHO guidelines (Hb< 12g/dl for adult female, <13 g/dL for adult male)
- **Selection of controls** : Individuals diagnosed without IDA
- Quantitative data (**Odds ratio**) defining association of IDA with HbA1c

Cross sectional studies: Studies analysing the distribution of HbA1c levels within a population assessed for IDA at a single time point.

Systematic reviews and retrospective analysis analysing the association between IDA and HbA1c in the Indian population

Outcome (O): Studies reporting quantitative and qualitative data on glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) levels and their association with IDA

Study design :

Both randomized and nonrandomized study types were included.

- Case control, cross sectional and systematic reviews studying the effect of IDA on HbA1c in the Indian population will be included in the study
- Studies in the English language from the year 2014 till date
- Studies with full text available
- Studies from peer- reviewed journals

Exclusion criteria

Population: Studies focussing on populations outside India

Intervention:

- Studies which used methods other than HbA1c to assess blood glucose levels
- Studies which assessed the effect of other types of anaemia such as megaloblastic anaemia, anaemia of chronic disease on HbA1c.

Comparator: Studies with factors other than IDA which affected serum HbA1c levels it such as

- Hypothyroidism
 - Hemoglobinopathies (HbAS, HbC, HbD)
 - Chronic kidney disease (altered renal function tests like increased serum urea, creatinine and glomerular filtration rate < 60 ml/min)
 - Alcohol ingestion
 - Smoking intake
 - Studies which assessed the effect of other types of anaemia such as megaloblastic anaemia, anaemia of chronic disease on HbA1c
- Studies which used investigations other than HbA1c to assess blood glucose levels

Study design

- Studies published outside India
- Non-primary studies
- Studies not published in the English language
- Studies with lack of full-text articles
- Non-peer reviewed articles

- Studies involving animal participants
- Duplicate studies

Search strategy

We conducted a systematic search on databases such as PubMed, Cochrane, Embase, Google scholar. from 19/07/25 till date. Articles involving the Indian population from 2014 to 2025 were included in the study. MeSH keywords were used with the help of Boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT) in different combinations such as 'HbA1c AND IDA,' 'Diabetes AND Anaemia AND India', 'HbA1c AND IDA AND India AND diabetes OR (non-diabetics)' and so on.

Reference lists of all the articles were manually checked using the Covidence software to identify studies not found by electronic screening. All articles were referenced using the Zotero referencing software. Data was stored in an excel sheet.

Study risk of bias assessment

Risk of bias was assessed using the ROBINS E for experimental studies and ROBINS I for interventional studies. Data was assessed independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences. Additional information was **not** sought from study investigators if required information is unclear or unavailable in the study publications/reports. The ROBVIS software was used to output the risk of bias(RoB) chart. The domains studied were (1) RoB due to confounding (2) RoB arising from measurement of the exposure (3) RoB in selection of participants into the study (or into the analysis) (4) RoB due to post-exposure interventions (5) RoB due to missing data (6) RoB arising from measurement of outcome (7) RoB in selection of reported result.

Data synthesis

In case of quantitative data , means and standard deviations of HbA1c and Hb levels in the studied population to be studied was extracted and tabulated in an Excel spreadsheet. Pooled effect size wae calculated using Jamovi version 2.7.5.(95% confidence interval). A random-effects model was employed.

In case of qualitative data, the study design, study sample and outcomes was tabulated in an excel sheet . The outcomes were listed narratively to summarize key findings and themes.

Certainty assessment

A certainty assessment was conducted using the GRADE (**GRADING of recommendations, assessment, monitoring and evaluation**) scale via the Gradepro gdt app. This helped us to analyse the risk of bias, limitations of the study, current gaps in literature and presence of confounding variables in the study.

1.6 Results

Literature search results

Table 1: Search strategy in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines

The database searches identified 80 related articles out of which 15 articles were excluded based on which were not relevant to our study. Out of the remaining 65 full text articles, 35 were excluded (Articles unrelated to IDA (n=10), unrelated to HbA1c (n=10)[10], and non-primary studies (n=4).[11] Thirty records were assessed for eligibility, out of which 13 were excluded (based on duplicity (n =1), Non-IDA anaemia (n=3),[11–13] studies sampling populations other than India (n=3)[9,14,15] uses methods other than HbA1c to screen for DM (n=2)[16]. No full text available or insufficient data (n=3), unclear outcome (n=2)[17]. Sixteen articles were finally chosen for the systematic review.

Results of synthesis

Quantitative analysis yielded a pooled effect size of 0.76 across studies (95% CI.), indicating a significant positive association between iron deficiency anaemia and elevated HbA1c levels in the Indian population. The results of the findings are summarized below in Table 2,3 and 4.

Table 2: Basic characteristics of case control studies included in the review

First Author and year	Experimental group	Control group	Study population	HbA1c (cases)	HbA1c (controls)	Hb (g/dL) (cases)	Hb (g/dL) (controls)	Detection method
Christy et al (2014)	70	50	DM	6.8±1.4	5.65±0.69	9.44 ± 1.36	12.54±1.4	HPLC
Chaudhari et al (2020)	36	36	DM (Type II)	7.15±0.78	5.81 ±0.38	9.69±1.68	13.81±1.06	Immunoturbidimetry
Patel et al (2024)	141	141	Non-diabetic	4.63±0.32	5.82±0.34	Not available	Not available	Immunoassay

Shwetha et al (2024)	50	50	Non-diabetic	5.78 ± 1.08	5.46 ± 0.26	6.414	13.4	HPLC
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DM: diabetes mellitus, Hb: haemoglobin; HPLC, high performance liquid chromatography

Table 3: Basic characteristics of cross-sectional studies included in the review

First author and published year	Study population		HbA1c (%)	Hb (g/dL)	Ferritin (ng/mL)	Method to assess HbA1c	Method to assess ferritin
Hari Krishna et al (2024)	Diabetic and non-diabetic	Group 1:	9.21 ± 0.9	8.81 ± 0.8	19.581 ± 6.313	Not specified	Not specified
		Group 2:	7.52 ± 1	13.42 ± 0.6	215.471 ± 76.92		
		Group 3:	5.84 ± 0.2	9.01 ± 0.9	28.28 ± 13.83		
Sk et al (2024)	100 non-diabetic patients with IDA ,	Study group	5.87 ± 1.25	8.69 ± 2.36	6.36 ± 3.98	Not specified	Not specified
	100 controls of same age and sex	Control group	4.97 ± 1.59	13.59 ± 1.88	116.69 ± 17.76		
Patil et al (2023)			5.67 ± 1.1 %	4.95 ± 1.310	24.28	HPLC	Bio-Rad QuantImmune Ferritin IRMA
Rajagopal et al (2025)	75 non-diabetic with IDA	Anemic group	6.84 ± 0.07	11.46 ± 0.08	12.09 ± 1.21	HPLC	Bio-Rad QuantImmune Ferritin IRMA
	75 non-diabetic without IDA	Control group	5.12 ± 0.04	14.31 ± 0.16	41.06 ± 0.43		
Janice et al (2022)	50 non-diabetic		5.04 ± 0.44	8.69 ± 1.79	18.17 ± 16.14	Immunoassay	ELISA
Srinath et al (2024)	150 patients	Group 1: 50 diabetics with IDA	8.69 ± 0.92	6.05 ± 1.76	48.86	HPLC using BIORAD	

		Group 2: 50 non-diabetics with IDA	5.87 ± 0.76	6.87 ± 1.73	57.06		Chemiluminescence immunoassay
		Group 3: 50 controls	5.03 ± 0.34	13.5 ± 1.1	120.58		
Gulavani et al (2025)	Type 2 DM	Cases: 100 IDA patients with type II diabetes mellitus.	8.1 ± 1.9	9.7 ± 2.4		HPLC	Not specified
		Control: 100 non anaemic patients with type II diabetes mellitus.	6.1 ± 0.3	11.9 ± 2.0			
Nebedita Dutta (2024)	Non diabetic with IDA	Cases: 60 IDA patients	6.5 ± 0.5	8.9	11.5	Latex agglutination	Chemiluminescence assay (CLIA)
		Control: 60 non-IDA patients	5.13 ± 0.8	13.7	178.5		
Kalairajan et al (2019)	120 with IDA	Anemic group	4.62 ± 0.30	6.8 ± 1.08	6.87 ± 1.5	Not specified	Not specified
	120 controls	Control group	5.45 ± 0.28	13.4 ± 0.35	232.26 ± 28.39		

Hb, haemoglobin; IDA , iron deficiency anaemia; DM, diabetes mellitus; HPLC, high performance liquid chromatography; IRMA, Immunoradiometric Assay.

Table 4: Comparison of HbA1c levels across diabetic and non-diabetic subgroups

Study date	HbA1c in diabetics with IDA	HbA1c in non-diabetics with IDA	HbA1c in diabetics without IDA
HariKrishna et al (2024)	9.21 ± 0.9	5.84 ± 0.2	7.52 ± 1
Srinath et al (2024)	8.69 ± 0.92%	5.87 ± 0.76%	5.03 ± 0.34%,

Bias risk assessment and quality evaluation of included articles

Risk of bias was assessed using the ROBINS I for interventional studies ROBINS E for experimental studies under the following domains .The majority of the interventional studies (Figure 2) showed a low risk of bias. However, the majority of the experimental studies (Figure 3)s assessed by the ROBINS E scale showed a very high risk of bias.

Figure 2: Graph assessing overall risk of bias in interventional studies

Figure 3: Traffic light plot assessing bias in experimental studies

1.7 Discussion

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disorder resulting from absolute or relative insulin deficiency. The International Diabetes Federation (IDF) reports that approximately 537 million adults globally suffer from DM, with a prevalence rate of 10.5%. [1] In DM, there is an increase in blood glucose (hyperglycaemia), which causes glycation of the phospholipid cell membrane. Glycation is a non-enzymatic chemical process, where glucose binds to N-terminal of β -haemoglobin in RBC's. [2,18,19] The American Diabetes Association (ADA) diagnoses diabetes at a HbA1c (>6.5%) The biological reference intervals of HbA1c are indicated below in Table1. Increased glycation damages the small blood vessels in the retina, kidney, and

peripheral nerves. This leads to chronic complications such as diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy, thus leading to a vicious cycle.

Other factors affecting HbA1c could be pregnancy, hypothyroidism and hemoglobinopathies (HbAS, HbC, HbD and HbE).

Anaemia is defined as the decrease in either haemoglobin or red blood cell (RBC) count below normal range for the given age, gender, and physiological status. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines, it is measured by the cut-off value of <12.0 mg/dl in adult non-pregnant women and <13.0 mg/dl in adult men [13]. Statistically, a study by Kumar et al. defines it as two standard deviations ($-2SD$) below the mean for the age and gender of the patient [12]. The WHO census conducted in 2016 estimates two billion of the world's population to be anaemic, with women in the reproductive age group and children under 5 being the most affected. It is a serious barrier to women and child health in Low- and Middle-income countries (LMIC's). Thus the epidemiology of anaemia is multifactorial and population specific.

The function of the RBCs is to deliver oxygen from the lungs to the tissues and carbon dioxide from the tissues to the lungs. This is accomplished by using haemoglobin (Hb); composed of heme and globin. Iron helps in synthesis of heme. One molecule of iron reversibly binds to four molecules of oxygen to form oxyhaemoglobin. Decrease in iron in the body decreases RBC formation. Therefore, there is development of IDA. This affects RBC structure and lifespan. [20]

Iron, folate and vitamin B12 levels reduce the rate of erythropoiesis. Thus they can contribute to the increase in HbA1c. [8]

A systematic review by Katwal et al. stated that IDA prolongs the lifespan of RBC's. [11][13] This increases glycation of haemoglobin, which leads to an increase in the rate of production of HbA1c. [13] A study by Aydin et al. stated that malondialdehyde, which is increased in IDA, promotes haemoglobin glycation. [20] These two mechanisms could contribute to a false positive HbA1c test in patients with IDA.

Majority of the studies in our systematic review showed that HbA1c was found to be higher in patients previously diagnosed with IDA. A cross-sectional study showed that there was a greater increase in mean HbA1c concentration in anaemic individuals ($5.59\% \pm 37.37$ mmol/mol), as compared to non-anaemic individuals ($5.34\% \pm 34.81$ mmol/mol) ($p < 0.001$). Cross-sectional

studies and retrospective analysis conducted in India showed that IDA significantly increased HbA1c levels[2,13,19,21–26]

Majority of the studies in our systematic review showed that HbA1c was found to be higher in patients previously diagnosed with IDA. A cross sectional study showed that there was a greater increase in mean HbA1c concentration in anaemic individuals (5.59 ± 37.37 mmol/mol), as compared to non-anaemic individuals ($5.34\% \pm 34.81$ mmol/mol) ($p < 0.001$) Cross-sectional studies and retrospective analysis conducted in India showed that IDA significantly increased HbA1c levels(2,3,9,16–23). Similarly, a case control study by Rajagopal et al ($p < 0.001$) showed a greater increase in HbA1c levels in IDA (6.84 ± 0.07) as compared to control group. (5.12 ± 0.04) [27] However a cross -sectional study by Janice et al showed that IDA decreased HbA1c levels, though the exact mechanism of this is unknown[28] These studies give contrasting evidence to other studies.

Hospital based cross-sectional studies by Hari Krishna et al and Srinath et al categorized patients into diabetics with IDA, non-diabetics with IDA and diabetics without IDA ($p < 0.05$) for further clarity.[8,19] They compared HbA1c, Hb and ferritin levels across the three subgroups,[19,21]. Results of Hari Krishna et al($p < 0.001$) showed that mean HbA1c levels increased in diabetics with IDA (9.21 ± 0.9) as compared to non -diabetics with IDA (5.84 ± 0.2) and diabetics without IDA (7.52 ± 1) [19] Similarly, Srinath et al ($p < 0.001$) reported an increase of mean HbA1c in diabetics with IDA (8.69 ± 0.92) as compared to non-diabetics with IDA (5.87 ± 0.76 and diabetics without IDA (5.03 ± 0.34)[8]

Most studies assessing the effect of IDA on HbA1c in non-diabetic women, showed that HbA1c was increased in subjects with IDA as compared to controls.[5,27] However , a case control study by Patel et al (n=141 cases , 141 controls) ($p < 0.0001$) showed contrasting results with greater increase of HbA1c in controls (5.82 ± 0.34) as compared to cases. (4.63 ± 0.32)[29] Similarly a study by Kalairajan et al which assessed the levels of HbA1c in patients with showed that there was a greater increase of HbA1c in controls (5.45 ± 0.28) as compared to cases(4.62 ± 0.30) ($p < 0.001$) However , the levels of HbA1c were increased in the study group (5.82 ± 0.32) after iron replacement.[30]

Analysis of results showed that high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) was used as the most frequent method to study IDA with HbA1c. (n=4)[8,21,24,27] Bio-Rad QuantImmune Ferritin IRMA (n=2) was the most frequent method used to analyse ferritin levels.[21,27]

1.8 Gaps in existing literature

The conflicting evidence across may be attributed to gaps in existing literature. Regional factors, including dietary practices, genetic predispositions, and healthcare access(8), have uniquely influenced the IDA-HbA1c relationship, necessitating a focused analysis. Most of the available data is based on single centre, hospital based cross sectional studies. Thus these findings may not be generalizable to other countries or healthcare systems. In resource limited settings, small sample sizes, variable population outcomes and variations in study designs lead to heterogeneity in results.

Further we did not exclude articles with pregnancy as the confounding factor which could have skewed the results.

1.9 Conclusion

This systematic review emphasized the importance of screening for iron deficiency anaemia prior to the evaluation of diabetes mellitus via HbA1c. By gathering information exclusively from Indian studies, it provided insights that were beneficial for clinical practice and public health in India. By combining data from several studies, it gave a good estimate of the link between IDA and HbA1c. The conclusions should be interpreted with caution globally due to variability in study designs, potential publication bias, and limited applicability beyond the Indian context. Future research should focus on comprehensive, multicentric, and methodologically sound studies that can corroborate these findings globally. This will reduce the risk of false positive /false negatives in screening for diabetes mellitus via HbA1c.

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Appendices

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Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest declared

Ethical clearance

The study is a systematic review and was based on previously published anonymized data. It did not involve human and animal trials. Hence ethical clearance was not required.

CRedit author statement

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